

Zenodo Upload Guidelines

Name of project: [Fostering high scientific quality in protein research in Eastern Slovakia \(CasProt\)](#)
No. 952333

Typeface of importance: **Bold underlined – required**, **Bold – recommended**, Normal - optional

1. **Upload** your document you want to upload to Zenodo to CasProt team files in MS Teams into folder “General\Data Management\Upload to Zenodo”
2. **Fill-in** at least required parts of PDF form “CasProt Zenodo upload requirements”, **save** your changes into the file with your name added at the end of original filename and then **upload** it to CasProt team files in MS Teams into folder “General\Data Management\Upload to Zenodo”
3. **Send** an e-mail with filenames of both files to CasProt Data manager (cas-prot@upjs.sk). If possible, please provide your phone number in case additional explanation to uploaded information will be needed
4. You will receive a confirmation on successful upload with Zenodo link by email

Information on licenses you can select:

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CasProt Zenodo upload requirements

Typeface of importance: **Bold underlined – required**, **Bold – recommended**, Normal - optional

1. **File name** - which file have to be uploaded from MS Teams folder

2. **Community (-ies)** – basic community is that one of Safarik University, another communities could be added

3. **Upload type**– select one item from whole list

4. **Basic information**

a. Digital Object Identifier – leave empty if not assigned to this upload; DOI could be reserved in advance in Zenodo if it have to be added into uploaded document

b. **Publication date** - date of first publication in format YYYY-MM-DD

c. **Title** - text

d. **Authors** – for each author write at least required information

Family name, given names - text

Affiliation - text

ORCID ID - text

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e. **Description** - text

f. Version - mostly relevant for software and dataset uploads - text

g. Language – primary language of record - text

h. **Keywords** – text

i. Additional notes - text

5. **License**– select one of four access right levels and for selected one add additional information

a. **Access right**

i. Open Access

1. **License**– select from list

ii. Embargoed Access

1. **Embargo date** - The date your upload will be made publicly available in case it is under an embargo period from your publisher in format YYYY-MM-DD.

2. **License**– select from list

iii. Restricted Access

1. **Conditions** – text - Specify the conditions under which you grant users access to the files in your upload. User requesting access will be asked to justify how they fulfil the conditions. Based on the justification, you decide who to grant/deny access. You are not allowed to charge users for granting access to data hosted on Zenodo.

iv. Closed Access

6. **Funding** - Grants – OpenAIRE-supported projects only. For other funding acknowledgements, please use the Additional Notes field. Start each row with Agency Code from list and then add Grant number, name or abbreviation

a. **Funding Agency** – select from list

b. **Grant number, name or abbreviation** - text

7. **Related/alternate identifiers** - Specify identifiers of related publications and datasets. Supported identifiers include: DOI, Handle, ARK, PURL, ISSN, ISBN, PubMed ID, PubMed Central ID, ADS Bibliographic Code, arXiv, Life Science Identifiers (LSID), EAN-13, ISTC, URNs and URLs. To each identifier add two character Relation code and optionally Resource code you find in lists below.

a. **Identifier** – free text

b. **Relation** – select from list

c. Resource type of the related identifier – select from list

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8. Contributors – for each contributor write at least required information and start with Role code you find in list.

a. **Family name, given names** - text

b. **Affiliation** - text

c. ORCID ID - text

d. **Role** – select from list

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9. References

a. **References** – free text, format of standard reference

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10. Journal

a. Journal title – free text

b. Volume – free text

c. Issue – free text

d. Pages – free text

11. Conference

a. Conference title – free text

b. Acronym – free text

c. Dates – free text

d. Place – free text, e.g. city, country

e. Website – conference URL

f. Session – free text, number of session within the conference

g. Part – free text, number of part within a session

12. Book/Report/Chapter

a. Publisher – free text

b. Place – free text, e.g. city, country

c. ISBN – free text

d. Book title – free text

e. Pages – free text

13. Thesis

a. Awarding university – free text

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b. **Supervisors** – for each supervisor write at least required information

Family name, given names - text

Affiliation - text

ORCID ID - text

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14. Subjects

a. **Subjects** – Specify subjects from a taxonomy or controlled vocabulary. Each term must be uniquely identified (e.g. a URL). For free form text, use the keywords field in basic information section.

Term - text

Identifier - text

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